

Building a Sustainable Joint between Rural and Urban Areas through Circular and Innovative Wood Construction Value Chains

D1.2

Building with wood as a driver for sustainable development in rural regions

Background and methodology for analysis of socio-economic impacts on rural development and rural-urban integration through wood construction

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Executive summary

The objectives of Deliverable 1.2 are to: 1) Describe the political, industrial, and market driven context for wood construction in Finland (pilot region North Karelia), France (Gironde), and Poland (West Pomerania); 2) Map the existing rural production – urban consumption relationships in wood construction; and 3) Set a framework for modelling and analyzing the socio-economic impacts of wood construction in the pilot regions by using North Karelia, Finland, as a case. Based on 3), we define the procedure for country and region wise analyses, which will be carried out in BASAJAUN WP7 *Open innovation platform and rural-urban pilot demonstrators*.

In both European and national levels, the recent policy actions set strong emphasis on wood construction as a tool to decrease the climate effects of construction sector. For example, the requirement to include low carbon criterion as a technical requirement for new public buildings at least in Finland, France, and Sweden during the coming years will apparently influence on the competitiveness of wooden solutions against other construction materials. Despite the climate friendliness of wood as a material within the construction sector, all use of wood has been put under question in the European Union in terms of the net climate effects of the utilisation of forest resources. It is crucial to understand that construction related uses of wood, *per se*, are not causing the climate issue, but the problem is their little volumetric share from all wood use: too large proportion of harvested wood ends up in short lifecycle uses currently.

Engineered wood products (EWP's) have enabled the revolution of wood as a building material in urban conditions. EWP's allow building larger and taller buildings than the traditional wooden single-family houses, second homes, and agricultural buildings in rural areas. Industrial prefabrication of wooden lightweight and easy-to-transport elements have changed the on-site activities from construction to assembly, allowing considerable savings in construction time and related costs. Turn-key deliveries of wooden house packages with an on-site installation time of approximately one day, have a stable foothold in the single-family house markets. They already represent majority of single-family houses built for instance in Finland.

Finland, France, and Poland differ clearly from each other in terms of wood construction traditions and current activity. For example, the shares of wood as a main structural material in single-family houses are approximately 1, 10 and 90 in Poland, France and Finland, respectively. Hence, promoting and increasing wood construction cannot rely on identical arguments or strategies in different countries. Instead, means to increase wood use must be reflected to the country-specific circumstances. On the other hand, it is evident that there is a great potential to increase the use of wood in large urban buildings, such as multi-storey residential houses, schools, day care centres, and sports halls in all three countries.

The region of North Karelia, Finland, which was analysed as a case region in this report, has set even more ambitious climate goals than the national ones – also pointing out wood construction among the means to achieve the goals. While being a sparsely populated and predominantly rural region, the construction activities, however, play a modest role in climate actions. We examined two building types, *i.e.*, single-family houses and second homes (leisure homes, cottages) both being almost completely made of wood in Finland nowadays. The report presents, thus, a case study on the regional input-output modelling of socio-economic impacts of single-family house and second home construction in North Karelia, Finland. The results indicate that wood construction possess a high potential for local economic development in North Karelia, particularly in the urban area around the

regional centre Joensuu, where most construction took place in the study period of 2011-2019. Based on the results, most employment impacts were allocated on urban areas because of the centralized production processes, while the impacts on rural areas were marginal. Interestingly, the employment impacts of second home construction are higher than those of single-family house construction in the rural areas. While the strong supporting impact of purchasing power of seasonal population on rural livelihoods has been known for a long time, the results of this study highlight the importance of seasonal population on the local economies via year-round job creation in the wood construction value chains. The average investment in wooden single-family house and second home construction was approximately 320 €/person/year in the region of North Karelia, which is approximately double *per capita* investment compared to, for example, milk.

The analyses of socio-economic impacts of wood construction will be continued in WP7 during 2021 and 2022 based on experience gained in this deliverable from the case of North Karelia, Finland.

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Glossary

<i>Acronym</i>	<i>Full term</i>
CLT	Cross-laminated timber
CLST®	Cross-laminated strand timber
ESB®	Engineered strand board
EWP	Engineered wood product
EPD	Environmental product declaration
GIS	Geographic information system
LAU	Local administrative unit
LCA	Life cycle analysis/assessment
LVL	Laminated veneer lumber
NEBI	New European Bauhaus Initiative
NUTS	Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics
OSB	Oriented strand board
PEF	Product environmental footprint

1. Introduction

1.1 Rural-urban definitions and development

Rural areas and regions in Europe have for long been defined and classified for the needs of international comparison and statistics, e.g., by the OECD and the EU, not to mention numerous national classifications. The United Nations Statistical Division (UNSD 2017) has stated that a uniform and global definition of urban and rural areas is not possible because national conditions and definitions are very different. This is also the case in the EU, where the differences in the regional structures and population densities of the member states are huge, especially in relation to the north-south dimension (Muilu & Rusanen 2004). This also makes it difficult to collect international regional statistics and accomplish urban-rural comparisons based on them. The UN therefore notes that each country must define its cities and rural areas based on their local circumstances.

However, the statistical office of the European Union Eurostat presented a new EU typology of “predominantly rural (PR)”, “intermediate (IN)” and “predominantly urban (PU)” regions applied from the OECD methodology in 2018 (Eurostat 2020c). The OECD approach is based on the percentage of rural population living in the local administrative units. Unlike the old typology, the new typology utilizes 1 km² grid cells and builds on identifying the population in urban areas by exploiting GIS methods. First, local units are defined on LAU2 level (LAU = Local Administrative Unit; LAU2 corresponds the municipality level) with a population density threshold of 300 inhabitants per km² and a minimum size threshold (5 000 inhabitants) to grouped neighbor grid cells for urban areas. The population living in rural areas is the population living outside these urban areas. Second, based on the population share in rural LAU2s, the regions are typologized as described above (Dijkstra & Poelman 2014; Eurostat 2020a; Eurostat 2020c).

The 1 km² grid is already available for Denmark, Sweden, Finland, Austria and the Netherlands and the new typology is based on the real grid in these Member States. For the remaining Member States, the new typology relies on the population disaggregation grid created by the Joint Research Centre (JRC), based on LAU2 population and CORINE land cover. The 1 km² grid is likely to become the future standard and has the benefit that it can easily be reproduced in countries outside the EU (see Eurostat 2020c for details).

The typology is based on LAU2 (municipality) level definitions but for statistical and comparison purposes it has been aggregated also to larger regional units. The Eurostat regional statistics exploits the NUTS system (Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics; the abbreviation comes from French: *Nomenclature des unités territoriales statistiques*), where the NUTS3 refers to provinces or corresponding regional units (Eurostat 2020b). Provinces are in most member states very important regional administrative units. The NUTS3 level is therefore the most relevant level for the regional statistical and other analyses in the BASAJAUN project since it matches also with the case areas. This depends of course on whether there are regional statistics available in the focus areas of the project on this level in the country and region in question. In some EU countries, NUTS2 is the only level being available.

Despite the potential that the Eurostat rural typology and the NUTS system provide to international comparisons, the fact is that each EU Member State have (even several) national typologies for rural

and urban areas. These typologies are also exploited in national statistics and regional analyses. Even though Eurostat compiles EU level regional statistics from Member States based on the Eurostat rural typology and the NUTS system described above, there are no comparable regional statistics available on specific themes, like wood construction. This causes that the chapters representing the situation of wood construction in the case countries and regions are based on national typologies and statistics.

1.2 Definition of “wood construction” in Finland, France, and Poland

In addition to the definitions of rural and urban areas, it is necessary to note that there are optional ways to define “wood construction”. Definitional country-to-country differences complicate the comparisons of statistical data, such as numbers of “wooden” houses built. One way to define wood construction is to concentrate on structural materials: if the load bearing structure of the building is made of wood, it can be called a wooden building. In this case, however, wood can represent only a minor share of all materials used in the building. Another way to define wood construction is to focus on buildings with wood as a dominant material, in which case the load bearing structures can be made of other materials such as steel or concrete, as well.

In Finland, the statistics are based on the first option: a building is classified a wooden one if its load carrying structures are made of wood. The same is true in Poland. Unlike in many other European countries, timber construction in France applies to any type of building whose construction is mastered by wood. The definition is not limited to load carrying frame but concerns all uses of wood in buildings (joinery, cladding, structural). It covers both new buildings and parts of buildings being renovated (boisREF 2021).

The intrinsic performance of this material in terms of energy and the environment, the structure of the companies that manufacture and implement it, make this sector an essential part of the response to the major challenges of the energy transition and the digital transformation. Whatever the general definition, the European wood-building sector is therefore promising in terms of employment, which takes place mostly in rural areas.

1.3 Objectives

The objectives of Deliverable 1.2 are to:

1. Describe the political, industrial, and market context for wood construction in Finland (pilot region North Karelia), France (Gironde), and Poland (West Pomerania) to understand the regional differences and conditions for development.
2. Map the existing rural production – urban consumption relationships in wood construction.
3. Set a framework for modelling and analyzing the socio-economic impacts of wood construction in the pilot regions by using North Karelia, Finland, as a case.
4. Based on the case (point 3.), define the procedure for country and region wise analyses that will be carried out in BASAJAUN WP7 *Open innovation platform and rural-urban pilot demonstrators*.

2. Drivers for wood construction

2.1 Megatrend of sustainability

The European wood construction market is changing, driven by sustainability related market forces.

- Firstly, the sustainable development goals (decreasing the use of non-renewable materials, carbon footprint and handprint of the construction materials, energy efficiency requirements, etc.) guide the construction, land use, and climate actions towards increased use of wood as a construction material.
- Secondly, the young generations are increasingly aware of the environmental impacts of their consumption behaviour. While their share from the whole consumption is still modest, one can expect radical changes taking place during the coming years and decades.
- Thirdly, wood construction materials, structural systems, and resource efficiency have developed tremendously during the last twenty years. This development enables high degree of pre-fabrication that minimizes the on-site assembly time, high precision and standard quality caused by automatized component manufacture, 100% dry prefabrication-transportation-assembly chain, predictable high performance allowing demanding structural applications such as high-rise buildings, as well as innovative architectural designs not only in small buildings but also in large ones.
- Fourthly, resulting from all previous megatrends, the public attitude towards wood construction has turned positive, even trend-alike, while still some decades ago wood was often treated either as a material of low-income builders or lower quality buildings. Nowadays wooden buildings are marketed by arguments of environmental friendliness, good indoor air quality, architectural versatility, fire safety, and naturality of the material.

Based on several good and bad examples worldwide, forests thrive as long the pre-condition of value creation for forest owners is fulfilled: raw material produced is an investment that must have an economic value (e.g., Heräjärvi 2019). The value is mostly created by wood product industries that buy the saw logs, use them in primary and further processing, and allocate the side streams to viable by-products. Since wood products are mostly consumed in construction value chains, it is evident that construction sector is an elemental contributor to the growing stock development. However, increased harvesting volumes may be a challenge for the goals of carbon neutrality if the use of harvested wood relies too heavily on short lifecycle products and energy. Analysis by Seppälä *et al.* (2019) indicated that increase in harvesting intensity with the current production structure represents a challenge for the Finnish forest-based bioeconomy from the viewpoint of climate change mitigation – even if the annual biomass increment is kept far above the annual removal. Instead of traditional forest ecosystem or techno-system approach they accounted for both eco- and techno-systems, which revealed the complex interdependencies between wood use structure and net carbon balance of wood utilization. The net carbon balance of wood utilization suffers from the small share of long lifecycle applications of harvested wood. Hence, wood use in construction applications, most of which represent long lifecycle, improves the general acceptability of wood utilization from the climate change viewpoint.

According to the World Green Building Council, buildings and built environment are responsible for 39% of global human derived climate effects. On the other hand, construction activities cover half of the exploitation of the natural resources and produce 40% of the waste globally. Therefore, already minor improvements in the sustainability of the construction activities make a big environmental difference. Wood appears to have a great contribution to this development, since it is the only renewable construction material available in industrial volumes, and features many other indisputable sustainability arguments, too. Recent research indicates that wooden interior materials have positive psycho-physiological effects on human well-being. Such findings may turn into powerful arguments for wider use of wood at homes and offices.

2.2 Policy actions in the EU

2.2.1 Scope

While BASAJAUN Deliverable 1.3 (Leszczyszyn *et al.* 2020) reviewed the EU policy actions dealing with construction and demolition wastes and, furthermore, cascade use of materials, this chapter of Deliverable 1.2 concentrates on the policy actions with existing or expected impacts on the development of wood construction sector. More information on the status of public policies encouraging the wood use in construction can be found in the recent review made for FAO by Mallet (2020). A short review on wood construction related policy development in 2020-2022 was presented by the WoodCircus EU project (Kleinschmit 2021).

Construction & demolition and new bio-based products represent two of the five priority areas in the EU Action Plan for the Circular Economy (European Environment Agency 2015). This calls for further improvements of long-term durability, cascaded life cycle management, value-added side stream utilization, waste management in closed loops, as well as energy and water footprint control in the wood construction value network. The transition towards bio-circular economy is facilitated by conscious management and intelligent utilization of natural resources, which aims at boosting the Europe's competitiveness, creating business opportunities and jobs, and increasing the overall sustainable growth and wellbeing of the European citizens. Shift from product-based to functional economy, in which functions of, for example, residential houses and public buildings are offered for the end-users, requires developed business models, as well as streamlining the regulatory framework.

Construction sector has huge economic, employment, and environmental impacts in the EU. Therefore, even small development steps improving the sector's performance, for example replacing materials with higher emissions by use of wood, can result in great torque for the environmental performance of the entire construction sector in the bio-circular economy.

2.2.2 Policy programmes

The policy basis for the development of wood construction at a European level lies originally in the targets of the *EU Bioeconomy Strategy* (European Commission 2012, updated 2018) and the *EU Action plan for the Circular Economy* (European Environment Agency 2015). The *European Green Deal*, aiming as a flagship to lead to European Climate Law, was published in 2020 to make Europe climate neutral by 2050 (Fig. 1) (European Commission 2019a). This includes an ambitious revision of 2030 climate

targets by a significant reduction of greenhouse gases. The Green Deal should become the leading pan-European programme in the shift from the linear to the circular economy. The objectives of the programme will be realized with a strong financial contribution through the European Green Deal Call, which is a European Commission funding call currently funded under Horizon 2020 and continuing under Horizon Europe.

Figure 1 Policy areas and key aims of the European Green Deal (Wall 2020).

2.2.3 Actions and initiatives

From the viewpoint of wood construction, the key initiatives to operationalize the European Green Deal are the *New European Industrial Strategy*, *Circular Economy Action Plan*, *Renovation Wave Strategy*, and new *Strategy for Sustainable Built Environment*, including *Construction Products Regulation* (Norton 2021). *New European Bauhaus Initiative*, *Ecodesign Direction and Sustainable Products Initiative* and *European Framework for Life Cycle Analysis (LCA)* are proceeding (Kleinschmit 2021, Norton 2021). In addition, preparations continue for the EU's *Biodiversity Strategy* and *Forest Strategy* (Norton 2021).

Bioeconomy is currently understood as a part of circular bioeconomy in the EU strategies and policy actions; therefore, bio-circular economy or circular bioeconomy has been often adopted as a combined approach in wood products sector and wood construction. The four-angle sustainability paradigm is acknowledged essential to integrate economic, social, and cultural aspects to ecological and environmental aspects in the strategic development and policy actions.

The key targets of the Circular Economy Action Plan cover sustainable products policy framework to promote the best materials and reuse/recycling options, legislative proposals to sustainable green claims with methods for Environmental Product Declarations (EPD) and Product Environmental Footprint (PEF), as well as regulatory framework for certification of carbon storage and removals. They may imply further improvements of long-term durability, cascaded life cycle management, value-added side stream utilization, waste management in closed loops, and material and product logistics in the wood construction value networks. Non-biocide-based durability improvement methods of

wood products, *i.e.*, wood modification, represent high potential to reduce the environmental impacts wood products exposed to water, soil, or weather exposure. To retain their environmental performance in the circular economy framework, the modification treatments should not compromise the recyclability of modified wood products in comparison to untreated or preservative impregnated wood products (Heräjärvi *et al.* 2020).

The EU's New Industry Strategy will support strategic EU value chains, including low-carbon industries and, hence, wood construction and wood product industries (European Commission 2019b). This means financial support to industrial and infrastructure investments and innovation, as well as research and development actions with high impacts to the sustainable growth in European bio-circular development. Institutional development steps, promotion campaigns, and technology innovations have already emerged novel industrial wood construction practices in some European countries, but most countries are far behind in the progress (Hurmekoski 2016, see also Winter *et al.* 2012). So far, rather little focus has been attributed to the organizational innovations, like understanding business logic or establishing novel business models, improving value networks and supply chains, or creating and sharing value add through collaboration of partners of the value networks (Hetemäki *et al.* 2017). In this respect, the European regions and countries have different opportunities and specific framework conditions, which can be observed as various policy actions and development priorities at the national and regional levels (Kleinschmit 2020).

The Renovation Wave Strategy aims at investments and support to increase the quality of building renovations, modernizing the construction sector, promoting the digitalization of buildings and the construction sector, promoting the circular economy, and informing citizens on sustainability issues (European Commission 2020a). The first target is to improve the energy efficiency, but low-carbon materials are considered as benefits.

The EU's New Strategy for a Sustainable Built Environment will focus on reviewing Construction Products Regulation into more circular with climate change mitigation goals (Parenti 2020). They may set requirements for recycled content in construction products and revision of material recovery targets from construction and demolition wastes. LCA approach on buildings to set carbon reduction targets will be obvious and level(s) in public procurement and taxonomy will be defined. EPDs and PEFs are intended to benchmark the products and create single, weighted, and normalized scores to show the impacts of each lifecycle stage. In parallel, European Framework for LCA is currently under establishment. Simultaneously, several EU member states prepare their national rules for carbon footprint estimation of new buildings. In Finland, for example, the Land Use and Building Act currently under renewal progress will make carbon footprint calculation of new buildings mandatory. The same progress is expected to take place in France already in 2022, and in several other EU countries soon after that.

NEBI, the New European Bauhaus Initiative is a discussion forum and meeting point of European construction related sector to support Green Deal, focusing on combining the interplay of sustainability, aesthetics, and affordability of construction (European Commission 2021a). The idea is to enhance the accessibility for and the participation of the citizens for all steps of construction chain and building development. Ecodesign Direction and Sustainable Products Initiative aim to shift from product-based to functional economy, in which functions of, for example, modern residential houses and public service buildings are offered for the end-users, requiring new advanced business models, as well as streamlining the regulatory framework (European Commission 2021c).

The EU's Biodiversity Strategy (European Commission 2020b) and the renewal of the EU's Forest Strategy (European Commission 2013) may have both short-term and long-term impacts on the availability and supply of wood-based materials from the forest to wood construction. They may indirectly affect the substitution of fossil-based construction materials and products with wood-based materials and products, and the competitiveness of virgin raw materials versus recycled materials in construction. The Biodiversity Strategy involves preliminarily the target to protect 30% of the EU's land and ocean area, including Natura 2000 areas, of which at least one third should be strictly protected. Increasing forest areas should be covered with "biodiversity friendly" management. Forest Strategy will include requirements for afforestation, forest preservation and restoration favorable to biodiversity. Wood import will be strictly assessed in relation to deforestation and legality.

2.2.4 Opportunities for implementation in wood construction value chains

According to Brannen (2021) there are six great opportunities of European policy actions that wood construction and wood product industries can use to increase their role in the bio-circular economy (see also GWM 2021):

- 1) Because the European Commission adheres the material neutrality, there is a high-level political support for the wood sector from the Commission, as it was emphasized in the State of the Union Address by President Ursula von der Leyen.
- 2) While the European Green Deal aims to make the European Union carbon neutral, wood can have a role there. In particular, the policy areas related to building and renovation in an energy and resource efficient way, as well as mobilizing industries for the circular economy. The European Green Deal involves eight hotspots, two of them supporting the use of wood.
- 3) The Renovation Wave is potentially important as wood can be in the core not only in the new built sector but also in the renovation. The Renovation Wave aims at the first stage to repair and upgrade 35 million European buildings for a higher energy efficiency and carbon storage during the coming 10 years. Wood represents a noteworthy option in this.
- 4) The New European Bauhaus Initiative can increase the wood use in renovation and complementary building of houses. Wood meets all three keywords of the initiative, and the sector needs to show how wood can contribute there. Five pilot projects will be launched for 2022-2023, whose results will be shared among the construction community.
- 5) LULUCF that was opened in the European Commission for re-evaluation because of tightening the targets of reducing emissions, may incentivize the harvesting of wood for long-lifecycle products. DG Clima has been appointed to work out how to incentivize wood in construction.
- 6) COP2, the United Nations Climate Change Conference 2020, to be organized in November 2021, is expected to refresh global climate targets, and indirectly boost the role of wood construction and rural development. The woodworking sector will showcase there to convince the policy makers that wood is among the solutions to fight climate change.

During the intensive discussion on the obstacles and opportunities of wood construction, which have been seen also in the context of EU policy actions, much attention has been paid on the national technical standards and regulatory aspects in different countries (e.g., Östman & Källsner 2011). The

debate has considered the methods and rules of life cycle analysis and other sustainability impact assessments, too (e.g., Rätty & Ito 2013). According to Brannen (2021), the biggest obstacles and threats for wood construction, to be solved in the EU legislation, policy actions, and promotion campaigns, are today related to the following questions:

- 1) Regulations and perceptions of fire safety – professionals and citizens still have negative opinions.
- 2) Availability of timberlands and supply of wood raw materials – industrial investments need a secure raw material supply.
- 3) Right to use wood residues as a source of bioenergy – European campaigns lead by NGOs and environmental activists gain much visibility, and politicians are aware of it.

Wood is acknowledged as a good construction material in the EU policy programmes and initiatives, but it has to compete in products and their use on a functional and material neutral basis, in the context of Neutral Building Competition Policy and Construction Products Regulation (Wall 2020). Hence, functionality, assessed by energy efficiency, climate friendliness, recyclability, or some other feature, should be the main attribute instead of the material itself. Subsequently, there cannot be an EU policy promoting the use of wood over other materials, and even using the word promotion may be problematic. Higher levels of wood use require a function-based approach to policy making at the EU, national, and regional levels. The functional and cost-benefit factors often highlight the opportunities of hybrid use of wood and other building materials.

Experiences from the COVID-19 may lead to new requirements on building design, space for living, and indoor air quality and control, possibly implying certain benefits for using wood in buildings, where human beings are present (Wall 2020). Connectivity of rural-urban relationships has also showed a new view when remote working, schools etc. became the reality, and multi-residence living has become a real alternative. FAO (2021) concluded the following messages from a global survey on what to learn from the COVID-19 for policy actions in the wood and construction sector:

- 1) Placing wood value chains in recovery measures and strategies to ensure that decades of advances towards sustainable development targets are not reversed as a result of pandemic: more efficient extension of social security schemes for forestry employees, reinforcement of legality programs, addressing informality, monitoring, enforcement, and licensing.
- 2) Provisioning timely and clear official information, as well as promoting awareness campaigns, are critical to allow adequate planning and implementation of responses to economic and social shocks: adoption of exceptional measures, developing organization both within the business environment and as a sector, adjustment of business strategies – very important for SMEs of forestry and remote forest communities.
- 3) Recognizing the need to provide financial support to SMEs: support to employment, cash transfers and subsidies to stay afloat, and staying capable to implement sustainable practices, certification schemes, and investments in innovation and digitalization.
- 4) Building legitimate partnerships and triggering better organization, cooperation, and coordination of forest value chains for poverty reduction: time of opportunities to organize and promote more inclusive, integrated, diversified, and shock-resistant value chains.

- 5) Strengthening forest governance will be critical to include the pandemic's impact and leverage contributions from the forest sector to the recovery phase: regular monitoring and enforcement to prevent the spread of unsustainable practices and illegal activities.
- 6) Promoting the trade and consumption of legal and sustainable wood products: sustainable forest management is crucial in the recovery to promote circular economy and climate change mitigation in the post-COVID environment.
- 7) Moving from the emergency to the recovery phase will require financial assistance: the COVID-19 will increase the demand for financial support in contrast to the tendency reported by the forest subsectors for these financial flows to decrease. Improving the data on the number of jobs and level of economic activity that the forest sector generates could facilitate its access to the international support and financing for the targeted actions on response to the COVID-19.

So far, urbanization, migration, and aging of people in the societies have stimulated the search for new solutions of construction for urban development. This is reflected in the current EU strategies and national policy actions. However, from now onwards the rural and urban policies may be focused more on two-direction interactions, value-add, and consideration of various aspects of social, cultural, and economic sustainability, at the national and regional levels at least. Accordingly, the recovery from COVID-19 may partly turn the building activity of residential houses back to small-house construction, in parallel of multi-storey buildings. Wood in construction is one of the most desirable directions of utilising the own resources of Europe, transferring from product-based to performance/functionality-based business concepts, implementing eco-design, and adopting cascading practices (Kleinschmit 2020). While wood construction falls under the category of broadly understood "green" and "sustainable" construction and fits into the basic trends of "future building", the foreseeable EU policy actions should lead to a stronger role of wood in construction sector.

The Rural Development policy of the European Union supports rural areas to meet the wide range of economic, environmental, and social challenges of the 21st century. The policy aims to achieve the following strategic objectives: fostering the competitiveness of agriculture; ensuring the sustainable management of natural resources, and climate action; and achieving a balanced territorial development of rural economies and communities, including the creation and maintenance of employment. Rural Development policy is referred to as the 'second pillar' of the EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), complementing the system of direct payments to farmers and measures to manage the agricultural markets ('first pillar') (European Commission 2021d)

The Rural Development policy is connected to rural-urban relationships via support to SMEs in the countryside. Therefore, the policy potentially provides benefits for rural wood construction value chains to improve their competitiveness and operative capabilities: timber production and harvesting, small-scale woodworking and construction enterprises, agricultural construction, and forest farm establishment. The policy bears also indirect implications through the development of transportation connections and data communications (digitalization). All in all, the direct impacts to wood construction are relatively small.

2.3 Policy actions in Finland

Finland is pursuing carbon neutrality as the first EU member state by year 2035. The Government programme (2019) of prime minister Sanna Marin’s government sets clear framework for timber construction in Finland. The aim is to double the use of wood as a building material during the reign of four years, set the objectives for wood construction in public building, and enhance the knowhow and overall development of the wood construction value chain. Implementation of these targets is on the responsibility of the Ministry of the Environment, which is the responsible Finnish authority setting the building codes and regulations. Specific objectives were set for public buildings (Ministry of the Environment 2020).

Ministry of the Environment of Finland published a roadmap for low-carbon construction in 2017. The aim is to add the low carbon criterion as a new technical requirement for buildings along with the renewal of the Land Use and Building Act that is expected to come into operation in 2023. Furthermore, the Ministry of the Environment set ambitious aims for the use of wood in public buildings by 2025 (Table 1). While the share of wooden buildings of all public building construction is approximately 15% now, it is expected to increase up to 45% by year 2025. Both these procedures are likely to improve the competitiveness of wood as a building material and add the use of wood in domestic construction value chains. In terms of volumes, single family house construction has traditionally been the clearly biggest wood user in the construction value chains. If the objectives for public construction will become true, the multi-storey residential building construction will turn into similar volumetric wood user than the single-family houses.

Table 1 Present state and objectives for shares of wooden buildings in public construction in Finland by 2025 (Ministry of the Environment 2020). Source of numbers of completed buildings: Statistics Finland (www.stat.fi).

	<i>Educational buildings</i>	<i>Buildings for institutional care</i>	<i>Multi-storey residential buildings</i>	<i>Assembly buildings</i>
	Share of wooden buildings from all new public buildings [%]			
Year 2019	31	6	3	7
Year 2025	65	35	46	30
<i>Total N of completed buildings 2019</i>	<i>271</i>	<i>128</i>	<i>885</i>	<i>139</i>

Finnish Government published a proposal for strategic programme “New Directions” to promote circular economy transition in Finland (Finnish Government 2021). According to the proposal, the transition into a circular economy means many opportunities and strengthens Finland’s export-driven economy and employment. Circular economy is expected to reduce the consumption of natural resources and the associated climate and other environmental impacts. The transition into a carbon-neutral circular economy requires comprehensive changes both in the decision-making and planning in society and in the attitudes and behaviour of companies, households, and consumers. One great challenge is to increase the productivity of the construction, which has not improved neither in Finland nor globally for 40 years (McKinsey & Company 2017). Due to the sectors high importance in terms of

economy, environment, natural resource use, and waste production, the Finnish “New Directions” programme sets heavy expectations on circularity of the construction sector.

The Regional Forest Programmes, prepared by Finnish Forest Centre (www.metsakeskus.fi/alueelliset-metsaohjelmat), have a sub-chapter “New wood-based products”. All 14 regions emphasize the role of wood construction as a tool to develop the forest-based value chains and livelihoods in the region, either as a main tool or among the most important ones. This reflects the high hopes set for wood construction by forest sector, as well as its overall visibility throughout the country.

The regional council of North Karelia in Finland has prepared an ambitious Climate and Energy Programme extending up to year 2040 (Pitkänen 2021). A roadmap to fossil-oil free and low-carbon North Karelia was published to implement the programme. The programme states low-carbon construction as one tool to reach the climate goals. Instead of being the actual purpose, wood construction is considered as a solution to reach the target, *i.e.*, environmentally sound low-carbon construction. Therefore, other construction materials can and are expected to equally contribute to the reaching of the goals.

2.4 Policy actions in France

French government wants to "Strengthen the sector starting from the markets, accompany companies and jobs on the path of innovation and digital transformation". Speaking on 18 April 2018 on the occasion of its visit to the Vosges on the theme of rurality, the President of France wished for a "voluntarist policy" to revive the timber industry in France: "Wood is a sector that we must develop in France. There are too few jobs created (compared to Germany, which has a slightly smaller forest area but generates twice as much added value and jobs). We must therefore set up a voluntarist policy, on which we are going to work with the sector". "This supposes massive reforestation, that we invest more", investments which will have to make it possible to "create a lot of jobs" by emphasising in particular "wood construction".

The Wood-Building sector (60 billion euros in turnover; 450,000 jobs including 250,000 downstream (secondary processing, building and services, Figures 2,3,4) is an integral part of the downstream sector of the forest-wood industry, through its ability to use wood material in the composition of all types of works, both in interior joinery and fittings, as well as in envelopes and structures.

Figure 2 Organization of the French value chain for wood construction in terms of turnover, workers by and main building sectors. Source: Observatoire des métiers du bâtiment (2018).

Figure 3 Description of the French wood construction value chain enterprises in terms of workers for main building sectors. Source: Observatoire des métiers du bâtiment (2018).

The intrinsic performance of this material in terms of energy and the environment, as well as the structure of the companies that manufacture and implement it, make this sector an essential part of the response to the major transition challenges in energy and digitalization sectors.

Figure 4 Carbon sink of French wood processing. Source: Contrat stratégique de Filière Bois (2018).

The wood construction sector is therefore buoyant in terms of employability, benefiting moreover from a context of a search for the meaning of work, which nowadays encourages orientation towards manual workers.

The markets for forest products (construction, furniture, interior and exterior fittings, paper, packaging, chemicals, energy) are the pillars of a strategy to win back customers and improve industrial performance. Indeed, they respond to major economic and social challenges. To achieve the carbon neutrality goal set for 2050, France is accelerating the pace of the ecological transition and the decarbonisation of the economy. The Filière Forêt-Bois (2018) renews its support for the Government's ambition with the future Environmental Building Regulations - known as RE2020. These regulations should enable the building sector (19% of carbon emissions) to play its part in decarbonising the economy. Therefore, the forestry and wood construction players are today making a solemn commitment to elected members, the French Government and their partners by launching the "Plan Ambition Bois-Construction 2030".

2.5 Policy actions in Poland

Due to a great shortage of dwellings in Poland (the estimate is 1.3-2.2 million), wooden construction is an important, a priority even, element of the housing support programmes recently. Wooden construction is in line with the actions envisaged in the National Housing Programme, which was adopted on the 27th of September 2016. It is a strategic programme document comprehensively describing the issues of the state's housing policy in the medium-term – by 2030 (the number of flats per 1000 inhabitants should increase from 363 to 435 during this period *i.e.*, to reach the European

Union average). This is an instrument for the implementation of the Responsible Development Strategy, which is based on the Dwelling Plus package. The programme promotes construction of affordable dwellings for rent with an option to become the dwelling owner eventually. The Programme is addressed to people with income too low to afford buying or renting a dwelling from the market, in the first place to families with many children. The aim of the programme is construction of single-family wooden houses and apartments in multi-family wooden houses. These investments are being executed by Polish Wooden Houses Joint-Stock Company (PDD S.A.), whose main line of business is „energy-saving wooden construction encompassing erection of residential buildings, management of these buildings and letting of residential buildings or apartments with the option of their sale“. The company was also established to intensify wooden construction in Poland (ecological and energy-saving) and to promote the use of wood in construction (as one of the possible ways of achieving climate neutrality). Construction of the first residential houses within the Programme was commenced already at the end of 2016. The company operates based on large resources of domestic wood raw material and the potential of the relatively well-developed Polish wood and construction industry.

The Act - National Housing Programme (act on facilitating preparation and execution of housing investments and auxiliary investments) sets forth principles and procedures of preparation and execution of housing investments (including investments on agricultural lands within city limits, on post-industrial lands, on post-military lands, on post-railway lands etc.) and auxiliary investments, as well as standards of those investment location and execution. In addition to the Dwelling Plus package, there are few programmes started to work, such as Apartment for a start (state aid regarding housing expenses in the first years of rental) and a support programme for Social Tenement Housing (based on preferential returnable financing granted by bank; it concerns not only new investments, but also refurbishments and adaptation of existing buildings). Self-governments executing housing investments are supported statutorily (construction of public housing and social housing).

Construction business in Poland are also to be facilitated by subsequent amendments to the Building Law. The law was to be pro-civic and de-regulative. The new regulations simplify and shorten procedures connected with construction work (reduce bureaucracy), they are to reduce the costs incurred by investors and ensure stability of decisions issued by offices.

In 2018, the Housing Council was established to coordinate activities for the implementation of the state's housing policy. In the same year, there was also a Forum of Housing Dialog – a Polish debate on the development of the housing market in Poland, which concerned all key challenges, *i.e.*, social, economic, financial, and legal. As a result of the debate there were established expert groups acting as analytical and consulting bodies to The Housing Council.

2.6 Revolution of industrial prefabrication and engineered wood products

Engineered wood products (EWP's), such as glulam, plywood, laminated veneer lumber LVL, oriented strand board OSB, cross-laminated timber CLT, cross-laminated strand timber CLST®, and engineered strand board ESB® are manufactured by gluing smaller pieces of wood together in order to form more uniform and free-dimensioned billets (*e.g.*, Smulski 1997, Heräjärvi *et al.* 2003, www.lignor.com) for structural uses. EWP's have upscaled timber construction from single-family and linked apartment houses to multi-storey residential buildings, schools, offices, and sports halls.

Good mechanical performance combined with homogeneity, *i.e.*, low property variance, allows structural designers to use lower safety margins with EWP's than solid wood products. Increasing the dimensions of EWP based posts, beams, or wall elements over those of traditional timber frame structures enables managing higher design loads and, thus, building larger or higher buildings. While wood's compression and tensile strengths are at least tenfold in parallel-to-the-grain direction compared to the transverse direction, EWP's with longitudinal grain orientation (glulam, LVL) exhibit the highest attainable performance under compressive or tensile stresses in applications such as load bearing vertical structures of high-rise buildings. This is one of the critical issues in high-rise buildings made with wooden load carrying frame, as well as long span structures, such as sports or concert halls.

The small-sized buildings in rural areas, such as single-family houses, summer cottages, garages, and storage buildings, are typically built and owned by private persons. In case of all these building types, the structural design is often based on either traditional timber frame or construction logs (either solid or glued), which are very cost-competitive solutions in small and medium-sized buildings. Urban areas differ from rural ones with regards to the type of buildings erected: smaller private projects are accompanied with larger buildings, such as multi-storey residential houses, office buildings, schools, sports halls, and religious assembly buildings. In case of larger building types, the technical-economic competitiveness of timber frame and log decrease and other structural materials gradually substitute them. Traditionally, these "other materials" have been concrete and steel. However, a reform of this paradigm has taken place during the last decades driven by EWP's and structural systems based on their application. EWP's have had an elemental role in the revolution of wood as a construction material of larger buildings, which are characteristic for urban areas. Hence, one can say that a) EWP's particularly serve the urban building activities, and b) they are indeed an enabling technology for modern wood construction development in urban areas.

Prefabricated volume elements are commonly used in multi-storey buildings already now. Many countries, including Finland, are however short of domestic manufacturers of them, resulting in considerable import of elements from Estonia and Sweden. To fully operationalize the potential socio-economic benefits and business development of increased timber construction, domestic production and use of domestic products should be strongly supported. Overall competitive ability of timber construction with other construction methods has improved much during 2010s, but there is still need for further development.

The unit weight (ca. 500 kg/m³) of wood is far lower than that of concrete (> 2,400 kg/m³) or steel (> 7,000 kg/m³). Therefore, wood is less expensive and more energy efficient to transport, handle, and assemble. Low weight also enables building extra floors on top of old houses without compromising the load bearing capacity of existing structures. Low material weight enables high degree of dry-condition industrial prefabrication because the light-weight elements can be transported to the building site by trucks. Logistics can be organised based on just-in-time delivery schedule. In an ideal case, a crane lifts ready-to-live-in volume elements from the truck to their final assembly position within a matter of hours. One can say that wooden volume elements have transformed a traditional construction site into an assembly site, which potentially reduces the on-site activity time by more than 50 per cent, subsequently resulting in considerable financial saving to the developer. Prefabrication of construction elements is more typical for wooden houses than concrete ones, because the truck load capacity and fragility of concrete limit the transportability of concrete elements. In addition, transportation and lifting of lighter weight wooden elements consumes less fuel and causes, thus, less carbon dioxide emissions compared to logistics of heavier elements.

3. Review of wood construction value chains

3.1 Finland

3.1.1 Production and markets

Houses and house elements are nowadays mostly built for the domestic market in Finland. According to Sipiläinen (2020), the value of wood house exports was no more than 45 million € in 2019, mostly covered by log house exports. The value of exported houses has decreased by almost 80% from the record year 2007, when the export value exceeded 200 million €. In terms of export value, Japan is now the biggest export market for Finnish wooden houses, consisting entirely from log houses. The other bigger export countries for Finnish wooden houses are Russia, Germany, and Norway. Wooden houses were imported in Finland mainly from Estonia (import value 47 million €), Sweden (15 million €), and Russia (2 million €). Another major turn took place in 2018, when the value of building renovation activities exceeded the value of construction of new houses for the first time. Table 2 presents the key economic and employment numbers of the Finnish wood product manufacture and furniture manufacture sectors. The total number of personnel working in those sectors was approximately 24,000 and the annual turnover was almost 9 billion € in 2018.

Table 2 Key figures of wood products sector in Finland (2018) according to the Finnish business sector classification. Source: Statistics Finland.

	<i>Wood product manufacture</i>	<i>Furniture manufacture</i>	<i>All</i>
Number of companies (share from all industries)	1,675 (8.4%)	806 (4.0%)	2,481
Turnover (1,000 €) (share from all industries)	7,523,458 (5.3%)	1,247,954 (0.9%)	8,771,412
Personnel (share from all industries)	18,425 (1.2%)	5,959 (0.4%)	24,384

Residential houses account for approximately 2/3 of the building stock in Finland, thus their building and renovation activities stand for great societal, political, economic, technical, and environmental importance. Timber frame and façade are already the predominant construction principles in single-family and linked houses as well as second homes (in this report, the leisure homes / cottages / cabins are referred to as “second homes”). Both in terms of wood volumes and business size, the biggest untapped potential lies in wooden multi-storey apartment buildings. However, wide range of educational and institutional service buildings indicate a great potential in public sector building, as well.

3.1.2 Building activity and structural systems applied

Wood itself provides high-level material properties for timber construction as regards the three basic requirements: stiffness and strength, dimension and form stability, and resistance against weather loads. The harmful variation in the technical properties that is typical for natural materials, have been largely overcome by applying intensive sorting, but also engineering and physical and chemical modification (e.g., Heräjärvi *et al.* 2020).

Figure 5 illustrates the development of construction activity for selected building types in Finland during the last 25 years. Total numbers of finished linked apartment houses and educational and healthcare buildings were some thousands and some hundreds per year, respectively, and they are not included in the figure. As seen, the building types, which have been traditionally dominated by wood as a main construction material (single-family houses and second homes), have experienced a dramatic decrease in numbers of finished buildings during the last 10-15 years. The change is also evidenced by the *per capita* annual wood product consumption, which used to be over 1 m³/person/a, but is currently approximately 0.5 m³/person/a. Low activity of single-family house construction is explained by the aging population and urbanization development; people have been moving in urban areas and multi-storey apartment houses. In terms of the share of population living in multi-storey apartment houses, among the European countries Finland is the second one, right after Spain.

Figure 5 shows only the numbers of buildings per building type. While the curve for multi-storey apartment house building activity (red line) indicates stable markets, the number of flats built in those houses has, in fact, increased dramatically. Approximately 10,000 to 18,000 apartments were built in multi-storey houses annually during the first 15 years of 2000s, while this number roughly doubled up from 25,000 to 35,000 flats per year during the last five-year period. Hence, houses with higher number of flats have been built, reflecting both urbanisation and aging of the population, as well as the lowering trend of the GDP in Finland during the past ten years.

Yet not visible in construction statistics, COVID-19 pandemic will apparently have interesting effects on wood construction. The trends of remote working and decentralisation, which have taken place because of COVID-19, appear to increase the rural demand of single-family houses and second homes, thus maybe turning the 60-year-long urbanisation trend into partial ruralisation. While these two building types are responsible for great majority of wood product demand in Finland, one can predict positive development for demand of wood product and building components not only in the public sector building (see Chapter 2.3) but also in the private sector.

Figure 5 Numbers of finished buildings of selected types in Finland between 1/1995 and 11/2020. Source: Statistics Finland.

According to Suomirakentaa market review (2019), the share of turn-key delivery or single-family house package delivery was 64% in Finland in 2019. The share of on-site building projects was only 10% and decreasing.

A somewhat hidden potential lies in concrete/steel/wood hybrid structures. Wood, wherever technically and economically feasible to use, can positively contribute to the overall environmental footprint and handprint of the building, even if considerable volumes of concrete or steel are being used. Hybrid structures also enable innovative solutions in terms of structural engineering, architecture, and interior design. Renovation and complementary building of multi-storey concrete and steel houses, either residential or commercial, in parallel to small houses is estimated to be a larger wood user than building of new houses. The needs and business potential around this activity will grow further, and provide a versatile demand for wood products, components, and elements, for example in facades, balconies, and extra floors.

Single-family house construction is common also in urban areas in Finland; approximately 50% of the single-family house construction took place in urban areas in 2019 (Table 3). A characteristic feature for Finland is second homes (cottages) that constitute an important building activity in rural areas. Almost 1,700 second homes were built in 2019, which almost one third of the number of single-family houses. While 90% of single-family houses, 99% of second homes, and 86% of linked houses are made with wood as a load carrying material (Table 4), those three building types make up the great majority of wood product use in construction value chains in Finland.

Table 3 Total building volumes and shares of wooden buildings in Finland and in the case region North Karelia in 2019. "Second home" refers to as leisure home or cottage. Source: Statistics Finland.

Building type	Single family	Linked	Second home	Multi-storey residential	Educational	Institutional care	Office	Assembly
N of completed buildings in 2019								
Finland	6,086	811	1,713	630	90	60	63	90
Urban	3,095	659	16	610	66	44	24	39
Rural	2,991	152	1,697	20	24	16	39	51
Finland wooden	5,422	679	1,676	22	57	45	39	57
North Karelia	192	24	48	12	1	2	4	4
Urban	38	8	1	12	0	1	1	2
Rural	154	16	47	0	1	1	3	2
North Karelia wooden	185	22	46	0	0	2	2	1

Table 4 Technical solutions applied in construction of new buildings in Finland, based on expert interviews.

Building type	Single family	Linked	Second homes	Multi-storey residential (N of apartments)	Educational	Institutional care	Office	Assembly
Estimated proportion from all buildings (including other materials) [%]								
Timber frame	64	84	23	2	15	25	12	1
Post-beam	1	1	0	0.5	1	1	1	6
CLT	1	1	1	1.5	1	2	1	1
Logs	25	1	75	0	3	1	1	1
Share of wooden	90	86	99	4	20	29	15	9

3.1.3 Case: Lighthouse Joensuu

Constructing wooden residential and office buildings became easier after the update of fire safety regulations in Finland in 2011. Now it is possible to build up to eight floors (or 28 metres) based on predetermined design values. Higher wooden buildings require functional fire safety design and detailed computation of the fire performance of the structures. The 14-storey Lighthouse Joensuu, finished in August 2019, is the highest wooden building in Finland, so far (Figure 6). The load-carrying

wall structures in floors 2-14 of this building are made of 162 to 126 mm thick LVL, whereas the floor slabs are made of 220 to 180 mm thick CLT, the material thicknesses decreasing from the base to the top. The whole building is anchored to the bedrock using 92 post-tensioned steel rods running through the building. The role of the steel rods is to eliminate wind induced movements: a challenge that needs to be accounted for if the weight of the building is low.

Total settlement of the 48-metre building during the first year was approximately 15 mm, *i.e.*, 1 mm/floor. Concrete is used only in the foundation and the first floor, while also the elevator and stair shafts are made of LVL/CLT elements. The siding material is virtually maintenance-free, through-coloured cement-fibreboard with four different colours and four gloss levels. Heating of apartments is based on water circulation pipes in floors, and the building is connected to the district heating network. Energy efficiency is improved by, *e.g.*, wastewater heat recovery system.

Building information modelling that enabled prefabrication of millimetre accurate fittings, inlets, and ducting, minimized the manual work after the modules were lifted to their final position. Lighthouse Joensuu, like all wooden buildings with more than two floors, is equipped with mandatory apartment wise automatic fire extinguishing system, which makes its fire safety superior compared to other construction materials.

Figure 6 Lighthouse Joensuu, finished in August 2019, is the tallest wooden building in Finland (14 floors, 48 metres). Architecture and main design: Arcadia Ltd. Architecture office. Photos: City of Joensuu.

3.2 France

The use of wood in construction reduces the greenhouse gas emissions by substituting other materials that are more polluting in terms of production and deployment (steel, concrete, etc.). Demand is growing and a recovery in the building market is taking shape since 2016. A few high-rise buildings made of wood are beginning to be built, such as the Sensations building (12 floors) inaugurated in Strasbourg in 2019.

Local initiatives are encouraging the integration of wood in construction or rehabilitation projects for public buildings, for which many local authorities are now asking for the use of bio-sourced materials. The health sector (hospitals, retirement homes) could also be an opportunity.

Table 5 presents the key economic and employment numbers of the French wood product manufacture. The total number of personnel working in wood product manufacture was approximately 27,450 and the annual turnover was over 4 billion € in 2018.

Table 5 Key figures of wood products sector in France according to the French inquiry of wood construction.

	<i>Wood product manufacture [Enquête nationale de la construction bois 2019]</i>	<i>French building overview</i>	
		2017	2019
N of companies	2,080 (60% have less than 10 employees)	392,000	403,000
Turnover (1,000 €)	4,010 (new building 73%, renovation 27%)	135,000	148,000
Personnel	27,445 (83% male, 17% female)	1,069,000	1,121,000

The share of wood in construction is still low but offers significant development potential (Table 6). In 2018, the share of wood in the housing market was 6.3% (5.9% in 2016) in France, against 17.8% in Germany (15.1% in 2014). In Ile-de-France in particular, the timber construction sector still only represents 0.2% of the regional market, despite strong demand for renovation, thermal insulation, and carbon neutral construction, due to the virtual disappearance of sawmills in the region. Timber frame is the leading technical solution in all wooden building types (Table 7).

Table 6 Total building volumes and share of buildings (wood, concrete, and masonry) in France.

<i>N of completed houses 2019</i>	<i>Single family houses, linked houses, cottages / second homes</i>	<i>Flats in multi-storey residential buildings</i>	<i>Educational & institutional buildings, warehouses, offices, agricultural buildings</i>
<i>FRA all, N of houses or</i>	175,400	235,700	
<i>Floor area (m²)</i>	19,138,000 m ²	14,477,000 m ²	27,689,000 m ²
<i>Urban (CoopHLM 2003)</i>	80% [+/-1.5%]		
<i>Rural (CoopHLM 2003)</i>	20% [+/-1.5%]		
<i>FRA wooden building</i>	14,955	10,700	1,145,000 m ² (10.5%)
<i>(market share) (enquete 2019)</i>	(9.4%)	(4.3 %)	717,000 m ² (18.8%) 1,561,500 m ² (25.2%)
<i>Nouvelle Aquitaine wooden building</i>		6,360	
<i>NUTS 1 (FRI zone)</i>	4,310	2,050	

Table 7 Technical solutions applied in construction of new wooden buildings in France (Enquete nationale de la construction Bois 2019).

<i>N of completed houses 2019 and floor areas (m²)</i>	<i>Single family houses, linked houses, cottages, second homes</i>	<i>Multi-storey residential buildings</i>	<i>Educational & institutional buildings, warehouses, offices, agricultural buildings</i>
		%	
<i>Timber frame</i>	84	81	75
<i>Post-beam</i>	8	9	15
<i>CLT</i>	5	10	10
<i>Log houses and traditional half-timbering</i>	3		
<i>All</i>	100	100	100

3.3 Poland

3.3.1 Basic information on wood and furniture industries

The main source of timber in Poland is the Polish forests. Contrary to many West European countries, the wood supply depends relatively little on foreign trade. In terms of the forest land area, Poland is the seventh largest in the European Union. However, the growing stock volume is the fourth largest and the roundwood removal is the fifth largest. Especially in furniture sector Poland is one of the global leaders.

In Poland, direct consumers of raw wood material are three industries of the wood sector, *i.e.*, sawmilling industries, wood-based panel industries, and the wood pulp industries, and, to a limited extent, the match-making industry. Wood is also used by consumers from outside the wood sector, in branches of economy such as construction (civil engineering), mining, agriculture, the electrical power industry, telecommunications, as well as by individual consumers. In recent years a new consumer of wood has grown in importance, *i.e.* the power sector. Foreign purchasers are also an important consumer group for Polish roundwood (export in 2019 – 4.6 million m³, approximately 10% of the harvest).

Gross added value in the wood sector (NACE 16, 17 and 31) in Poland in 2019 accounted for 9% of the total value in industry (wood and furniture industry 6% respectively). The furniture industries had the largest share in generating gross added value in the wood sector (more than 38%; 55% in wood and furniture industry). Sold production in the wood and furniture industry (NACE 16 and 17) in Poland was 21.7 billion € and accounted for 5.8% of its value in industry in total and for 6.7% of its value in manufacturing (Table 8). Index of sold production (in constant price) in the wood and furniture industry was lower than in industry and manufacturing and equaled 4.8% in the wood industry and 4.6% in the furniture industry. In the branch structure of the wood products sector sales in 2019 was dominated by the furniture industry with a more than 54% share, while the share of wood industry was approximately 46%.

The number of enterprises in the wood industry in Poland amounted to 60,600 in 2020 (they accounted for about 17% of total industry and 18% in manufacturing and almost 2% of all registered economic entities). Approximately half of the entities (51%) operated in the wood industries (31,000) and 49% were registered in the furniture industry (29,600).

Regarding the labour market situation in Poland, it is estimated that the wood and furniture industry employed 290,000 people in 2019, of which 61% in the furniture industries and 39% in the wood industries. The share of this sector within total employment in the industry and manufacturing sectors was 10% and 11%, respectively.

Table 8 Key figures of wood and furniture industry in Poland (2019) according to NACE 2007 classification.
Source: Statistics Poland

Specification	Wood product industry (sector 16)	Furniture industry (sector 31)	Total
Number of companies* (share of total industry)	30,964 (8.5%)	29,595 (8.1%)	60,559
Sales (million €) (share of total industry)	9,959 (2.7%)	11,707 (3.1%)	21,666
N of employees (share of total industry)	114,600 (3.9%)	175,600 (6.0%)	290,200

* N of companies (entities of the National Economy Recorded in the Region Register (excluding persons conducting private farms in agriculture): as of March 31, 2020.

3.3.2 Construction and assembly production

The value of construction and assembly production realized in Poland in 2019 amounted to 56.4 billion €. including the sale of construction works realized with own resources (*i.e.* without subcontracting) by construction companies in the amount of 53.4 billion € (94.7%). The remaining 5% of production consisted of production realized with a contract system by non-construction companies¹ and works carried out based on own-account construction. In the period 2015-2019, construction companies accounted for 94% of the total value of construction and assembly production realized in Poland. Construction and assembly production in 2019 increased by 5.7% in comparison to the previous year, including an increase in the value of production realized by construction companies by 5.5%.

Almost all construction and assembly production of construction entities realized in Poland in 2019 was attributable to private sector entities. In the last five-year period (2015-2019), the share of the public sector did not exceed 1%. Entities with up to 9 employees generated more than half of the value of construction and assembly production (51.6%), realized with own resources (without subcontracting). The share of microenterprises in the total value of construction and assembly production of construction entities in last five-year period was at a similar level. However, the construction and assembly production generated in Poland in 2019 by large and medium-sized construction entities (more than 9 persons employed) with their own resources amounted to 26.8 billion € and was 5.7% higher than in 2018.

The value of construction and assembly production generated outside of Poland in 2019 by Polish construction and non-construction entities amounted to 1.6 billion € (entities employing more than 9 persons and with their own resources). Nearly 89% of this sum (1.4 billion €) was related to construction enterprises. Calculated per 1 employee performing these works, it amounts to 63.2 thousand € *per capita*. The value of construction and assembly production export in Poland in 2019

¹ Construction companies are understood as economic entities whose main type of activity is included in the section F "Construction" in NACE classification. Companies whose activities have been included in sections other than "Construction" in the publication are referred to as non-construction.

increased by 2.9% in relation to 2018, including works carried out by construction entities – by 1.7% (in current prices). More than 52 per cent of the total value of construction and assembly production carried out abroad in 2019 was related to works performed in Germany. This tendency was observed also in the previous years. Construction works performed in Sweden (7.3%), Belgium (7.2%) and Norway (6.1%) also had a large share in the value of construction and assembly production.

3.3.3 Construction industry

The construction industry has an influence on the situation in other areas of the economy, such as the production of building materials, furniture, and home furnishings. The development of the construction industry creates jobs in industry, services, and other related industries, including in the wood products industries. It also performs very important social functions, mainly in terms of housing construction, conditioning the increase in the standard of living of the society as well as the progress of civilization.

In 2019, compared to the previous year, there was an increase in the number of new non-residential building completed in Poland, and the total area of new buildings. Increasing tendencies were also observed in the case of issued construction permits or submitted notifications of construction projects. There has also been an increase in the number of residential buildings completed in Poland in 2019 (this increase was 8.1% compared to the previous year and 11.8% compared to 2015) (Figure 7). Compared to last year, the number of newly constructed single-family houses and multi-family houses also increased (an increase of 4.5% and 22.2%, respectively).

Figure 7 New residential buildings completed in Poland in 2015-2019 (Source: Statistics Poland).

In 2019, there were 85,700 new residential buildings completed in Poland, 77.3% of which were single-family houses (66,200) (Table 9). In Poland, wooden houses constitute only approximately one per

cent of all new residential buildings completed², and over 90% of those are single-family houses³. In the case of the West Pomeranian Voivodeship, the number of residential buildings completed in 2019 amounted to 2,700 (which was slightly below the average), dominated by single-family houses (73.8%). Only 36 wooden houses were built in this voivodeship in 2019, of which 35 were single-family houses.

Table 9 Number of new residential building in Poland in 2019 (case region: West Pomerania). Sources: Statistics Poland.

<i>Specification</i>	<i>Single-family houses</i>	<i>Multi-family houses</i>	<i>Total</i>
Poland, all	66,237	19,471	85,708
Wooden	641	67	708
West Pomerania	2,026	719	2,745
Wooden	35	1	36

In 2019, compared to the previous year, there was an increase in the number of new non-residential buildings completed in Poland (by 0.5%), more than 23,000 of such buildings were built (Table 10). In terms of the number of new non-residential buildings completed for use in Poland, in 2019 the group "Other non-residential buildings" (37.5% of the total) was dominant, with the largest share in the class "Farm buildings" and the group "Traffic and communication buildings" (22% of the total). Regarding the "urban-rural" perspective, 63.6% of new non-residential buildings were built in rural areas.

² According to experts, official statistics on the number of wooden houses in Poland are underestimates. It is estimated that approximately 5,000 wooden houses are built in Poland annually, which is a 6-7% share of the single-family houses completed per year. Moreover, it is estimated that around 4,000 houses are additionally built by Polish companies abroad.

³ Currently, wooden multi-storey construction in Poland is practically non-existent, mainly due to fire regulations, which allow for the construction of buildings with wooden structures up to 12 m high (*i.e.*, maximum 4 floors).

Table 10 Number of new non-residential buildings in Poland in 2019 (case region: West Pomerania). Source: Statistics Poland.

	Hotels and similar buildings	Office buildings	Wholesale and retail buildings	Traffic and communication buildings	Industrial buildings and warehouses	Public buildings *	Other non-residential buildings	Total
N of buildings completed in 2019								
Poland	1,776	574	2,838	5,069	3,397	744	8,644	23,042
Urban	404	360	1,694	2,801	1,785	338	995	8,377
Rural	1,372	214	1,144	2,268	1,612	406	7,649	14,665
West Pomerania	776	24	137	144	141	47	155	1,424
Urban	88	16	89	99	94	16	35	437
Rural	688	8	48	45	47	31	120	987

* Public buildings: buildings for public entertainment, education, hospital or institutional care buildings, and sports halls.

In the case of the West Pomeranian Voivodeship, the number of non-residential buildings completed in 2019 in Poland amounted to 1.4 thousand, more than half of them were "Hotels and similar buildings" (54.5%). As in the case of Poland in general, in the West Pomeranian, new non-residential buildings completed occurred more frequently in rural areas (more than twice).

3.3.4 Wooden house market

Despite the growing interest in wooden construction as an instrument to satisfy the housing needs of the society, so far in Poland there is not enough systematically provided and up-to-date information on the market of wooden houses. Data from the Central Statistical Office reporting, collected from several reports within the framework of public statistics surveys, inform only to a small extent and very fragmentarily about the situation in this segment of the domestic construction industry. However, they are often incoherent and therefore cannot be the basis for a comprehensive analysis of this market.

In the official statistics of Poland, there is a lack of information on the contractors of wooden houses - in the National Business Registry Number in section F: "Construction" of the Polish Classification of Activities (NACE 2007), in group 41.2 "Construction works related to the construction of residential and non-residential buildings" it was registered in at the end of March 2020, almost 109 thousand

companies, most of them (95%) were small companies employing less than 10 people. However, wood house contractors cannot be separated from this number. Therefore, it is estimated that there are approximately 800 such companies in Poland (according to the database of the Wooden House Association). Approximately 530 companies build wooden houses in the wood-frame system (including 60-80 companies fully prefabricated), almost 260 companies build log houses. Most of them are small companies, only 30-40 companies have a greater production potential. There are also companies on the market that only produce wooden summer houses (however, their number is difficult to determine). It is estimated that the potential of the Polish wood construction industry is not fully used, mainly due to insufficient demand and also due to labor shortages (experts assess that in some companies building wooden houses, the production capacity could be even below 50%).

The demand for Polish timber houses is largely generated by foreign buyers. According to the Central Statistical Office, weight of almost 46,000 tons of prefabricated wooden buildings, worth 66.8 million €, were delivered to foreign markets in 2019. The main export markets were Norway (31% in terms of value), Germany (28%), Great Britain (8%), and the Netherlands (8%). In turn, experts estimate that approximately 4,000 Polish wooden houses are built abroad every year. Some companies export 100% of their production.

On the other hand, the import of wooden houses to Poland is relatively small (mainly wood and roofing materials are imported). According to expert estimates, approximately 50 house units are imported per year (e.g., log houses from Finland). According to the Central Statistical Office of Poland, weight of 6,700 tons of prefabricated wooden buildings, worth 5.4 million €, were imported in Poland in 2019. The most important import countries were Russia (52% of the value) and Ukraine (33%).

3.3.5 Technologies used in wood construction

Use of modern construction solutions allows construction of diverse buildings, also interesting architectural solutions. There are two main wood construction systems applied in Poland: timber frame and log houses. In the case of timber frame houses, three structural systems dominate:

- Linear frame construction (light wooden frame) characterized by the performance of structures on the construction site from individual elements.
- Linear prefabricated construction characterized by the erection of buildings on a construction site with elements prepared under controlled factory conditions.
- Prefabricated spatial construction systems, so-called modular construction.

Log houses are usually built in Poland in two ways. The most common system for building log houses is Interlocked corner structure. The second system of wall construction in log houses is the post-and-plank log structure⁴.

⁴ Post-and-plank log structure: the method of building wooden houses with a traditional timber frame with horizontal plank or log infill between grooved vertical posts (pièce sur pièce in French, Ständerbohlenbau in German, skiftesverk in Swedish, and sumikowo-łatkowa in Polish).

It is estimated that approximately 50% of the Polish companies build wooden houses on the construction site, while the other companies either produce partially prefabricated elements and finish them on the construction site (approx. 40%) or use fully prefabricated elements (approx. 10%). Modular houses are produced by less than 5% of the wooden house manufacturer companies. There is also one company in Poland specialized in production of prefabricated elements, while not building wooden houses itself.

Wood frame-houses account for 75% of the wooden single-family houses in Poland (Table 11). In the structure of wood frame-houses, the most common are prefabricated houses (42%). Linear frame construction houses also have a relatively large share (32%). On the other hand, log houses account for 25% in the structure of the most frequently build wooden houses.

Table 11 Share of the type of structures used in wooden single-family houses in Poland. Sources: Opinions of experts from the Łukasiewicz Research Network - Wood Technology Institute supported by market research in Poland.

<i>Type of structure</i>	<i>Single-family houses</i>
Timber frame houses, including:	75%
<i>Prefabricated houses</i>	42%
<i>Linear frame construction</i>	32%
<i>Modular houses</i>	1%
Log houses	25%

The technology of manufacturing houses using the prefabrication method has been developing very intensively in recent years in Poland, but a significant part of their production is used to build houses outside Poland. There is also a noticeable increase in interest in building public buildings, including schools and nursery homes using prefabricated timber frame.

According to market analyses, the most frequently used wood material for the construction of wooden houses in Poland is solid structural wood (coniferous wood) and solid construction timber with joints (KVH), 85 and 70 per cent of the companies use them in production, respectively. Cross-laminated timber (X-Lam, CLT) is rarely used in the construction of wooden houses in Poland.

The wood materials used by the producers come from Poland and abroad. Laminated veneer lumber (LVL), I-joists, as well as most of plywood and other wood-based panels are estimated to be of domestic production. Solid construction timber with joints (KVH), as well as structural lumber and glulam are mostly imported.

3.3.6 Future aspects

In the coming years, wooden construction in Poland has a chance to develop, but certain requirements must be met. There should be regulations and standards regarding the provisions on wooden construction included in the Construction Law Act (*e.g.*, concerning fire safety, height of building structures). It is also necessary to educate architects, designers, inspectors and the public in the field of wooden construction, as well as continuous, effective promotion of this construction in society. It is also important to convince investors to change their attitude to this type of construction. This should be due to the greater availability of innovative wood materials, the properties of which allow for great freedom in designing and building wooden houses. It should also be expected that wooden construction will not be limited only to single-family houses but will become more common in development in multi-storey construction (also non-residential).

4. Rural production – urban consumption: rural-urban linkages

4.1 Socio-economic impacts of wood construction in Finland

The socio-economic impacts of the wood construction for urban and rural areas are known insufficiently. So are the possibilities and linkages of the construction to change the negative areal development trends into positive ones in rural areas.

Esala *et al.* (2012) estimated that the impacts of increasing wood construction on Finnish economy are positive. Increased use of domestic wood products decreases the need to use imported products, *e.g.*, steel, which in turn increases the domestic tax revenues and employment. Investments in wood element production would create further jobs in rural areas. However, since Finland is a net exporter of wood products (approximately 70% of the production is exported), increase in domestic wood construction does not necessarily mean increments in production of primary wood products such as sawn timber or plywood, since domestic use and exports are at least partly interchangeable.

Among the Finnish regions, the region of Northern Ostrobothnia is the second biggest in terms of number of wooden house manufacturers (21 in total in 2017) and the biggest in terms of their annual turnover (in total 183.6 million € in 2017). The total number of wooden house manufacturing companies has decreased by some 20% during the past ten years. However, within the wooden house manufacturing business, one segment has increased up to approximately 30 companies, mostly rather young SME's. This segment is the producers of wooden elements for large-scale buildings (multi-storey apartment houses, public buildings). Growth in production of industrially prefabricated modules and building elements is clearly visible in the employment figures: the number of people working in element manufacture has doubled in Finland during the past five years. Now there is a lack of skilful workers, as well as structural designers for demanding wood construction projects.

Männistö *et al.* (2012) estimated the economic influence of wood construction in Southern Ostrobothnia region in western Finland. They used two different settings in defining the role of construction value chains in the regional economies. The first one was based on idea of open economy, *i.e.*, the raw materials and equipment are purchased by optimized price and logistics costs. Hence, for example the building materials can be imported from outside of the region, if it is the cheapest way. The other setting was based on idea of closed economy, in which all or the most important materials are purchased from the region. Männistö *et al.* (2012) reported that wood construction sector provides added value to the regional economy in both open and closed economy settings. They estimated that in the open economy setting an investment of one Euro to the wood construction generates another Euro in other regional economy, whereas in the closed economy setting the multiplying effect was two times bigger.

4.2 Socio-economic impacts of wood construction in the Region of North Karelia

4.2.1 Description of the region

The purpose of this chapter is to describe and analyze the socio-economic impacts of wood construction on urban and rural areas and introduce the recent development and current changes of wood construction in a case region, North Karelia, in Finland. We focus on analyzing the employment impacts of the construction of single-family houses and second homes (cottages). In comparison to apartment buildings, these building types offer spatially different patterns for wood construction, as second home construction concentrates on rural areas due to counter urbanization, while single-family house construction is driven by urbanization led by the biggest regional centers. In Finland, second homes are very popular, and it is estimated that 2.2 million people (40% of population) use second homes annually. The average population of the rural areas in the North Karelia in July is estimated to be over 60,000 inhabitants higher than the permanent population of 160,000.

The region of North Karelia has a very strong bioeconomy sector. The region employs approximately 600 forest bioeconomy experts in research and education organizations. The forest bioeconomy success story is a result of 40 years of determined work. Nowadays 35% of the annual turnover and 10% of the jobs in the region are based on forest bioeconomy. North Karelia is globally known by the forest bioeconomy research and education, led by activities of Natural Resources Institute Finland, University of Eastern Finland, European Forest Institute, Finnish Environment Institute, and Karelia University of Applied Sciences. In addition to a leading position in the forest research, the region focuses on multi-disciplinary approach to develop novel tangible and intangible product and service innovations around the bioeconomy sector. One example is international master's degree programme in wood materials science, the largest educator of wood scientists in Finland, broadly combining the disciplines of applied physics, biology, chemistry, and forest sciences. Another example is the service innovation platform Wood Hub©, a joint approach of eastern Finnish RDI-organizations to facilitate collaboration in the field of wood technology and wood construction development. The North Karelian bioeconomy actors rely on interdisciplinary and cross-sectoral development that has proven to be a productive way to create high value-adding business in, e.g., cascade use of materials.

Despite of the positive development of the bioeconomy sector, the projected population development set a real challenge for the aging and shrinking municipalities and poses a threat for economic development of the region. For instance, the forest resources are increasingly being utilized through the labour force living in the municipal centres, because the supply of competent labour in the distant and core rural areas has been on the decline (Lehtonen & Tykkyläinen 2008), but in the future the labour shortage will also be severe in the municipal centres.

The region of North Karelia accounted for approximately 2% of the volume of completed buildings in Finland in year 2018 (Statistics Finland), which corresponds to the share of region's population from the population of Finland. In total, 39 per cent of the volume of completed buildings had wooden load bearing frame in the region of North Karelia in 2018. There were seven producers of wooden houses, with combined annual turnover of approximately 4.4 million €, in the region of North Karelia in 2017. All producers are SME's, and most of them are small family owned companies with less than ten employees.

North Karelia is one of the 20 regions in Finland and has the size of approximately 2/3 of Belgium. North Karelia is located at a coniferous zone in the easternmost part of the country. It is an example of a resource-dependent NUTS3 level region in the north of Europe, increasingly boosted by state-led innovation policy and various regional policy projects. It is also an example of the single-nodal region where development is mainly concentrated in the regional capital city Joensuu and its surroundings. Population growth reverts to a decline as a function of distance from the core of the region and is negative in the areas outside the travel-to-work area of Joensuu. Among the 12 municipalities of the region, only Kontiolahti, which is located next to Joensuu, has a steady positive development in population. A decrease in total population has taken place and is projected to be the most severe in the most distant areas (Fig. 8).

Figure 8 Population 2000-2019 and population projection 2020-2040 by municipalities in North Karelia. The municipalities are positioned according to their true geographical locations.

4.2.2 Methodology

Here, we analyze the rural-urban linkages in wood construction based on Geographic Information System (GIS), which is combined with regional input-output modeling. GIS is a collection of techniques applied with spatial data and it is used for processing, analyzing, and interpreting spatial data based on spatial information: coordinates, address information or zip code, for instance. GIS methods can reveal where things are and what is their spatial relationship. Thus, they offer an opportunity to a detailed analysis of the spatial pattern of wood construction in North Karelia during a study period 2011-2019. The study uses basic GIS operations, such as spatial join, to combine wood construction statistics with urban-rural classification. The flowchart of the analysis is demonstrated in Figure 9.

Figure 9 Flowchart of the analysis modelling the employment impacts of the wood construction.

4.2.3 Statistics for wooden single-family house and second home construction

The construction statistics were provided by Digital and Population Data Services Agency of Finland from real estate, building and spatial information registry. This data contains very thorough information of all the registered buildings, and it is maintained by National Land Survey of Finland. These statistics include both building and façade materials for most of the buildings, which made it possible to compare the share of wood construction to the other types of construction, for instance. The coordinates of the buildings enabled combining their locations with the GIS-based urban-rural classification by using spatial join GIS operation. The use of GIS-based urban-rural classification allows detailed analyses of the wood construction and its urban-rural linkages, which is an important element of the socio-economic impact assessment.

Figure 10 shows the urban-rural classification in the study region, which is used to analyze the urban-rural linkages in wood construction. In the GIS-based urban-rural classification, 250 m × 250 m grids are divided into 3 urban and 4 rural categories. The classification is based on the variables describing population, labour, commuting, building and land use characters of the areas. Based on these variables the areas have been divided into urban-rural categories by using a variety of analyses and

classification rules (Helminen *et al.* 2014; see Data and Methods for the description of the YKR georeferenced statistical database). All urban areas - inner urban area, outer urban area, and urban fringe - are combined into one category in Figure 10. Rural areas are classified into four categories: 1) local rural centres, 2) rural areas close to urban areas, 3) core rural areas, and 4) sparsely populated rural areas, reflecting different characteristics of the rural areas. Local rural centres that are outside the larger urban areas are small towns and large church villages. Rural area close to urban area is a rural area that is functionally and physically close to urban area. Core rural areas are described as intensive land use and relatively densely populated rural areas with a diverse economic structure at local level. Sparsely populated rural area is an area with no or small concentrations with diverse activities and located far from each other. Most of the land in the area is forest.

These four categories of rural areas have been characterized by a loss of population in North Karelia. Only rural areas close to urban areas have had relatively stable population numbers as population has declined during 2011-2019 by only 4.4%. The remaining three rural categories have experienced a significant loss of population. Most severe population losses have occurred in sparsely populated rural areas where the loss of population was 15.5% in 2011-2019. The population losses in local rural centres and core rural areas were 10.6 and 12.3 per cent, respectively. At the same time, in urban areas the population growth was 8.7%.

Figure 10 also visualizes the spatial distribution and density surfaces of the constructed wooden single and second homes in North Karelia between 2015 and 2019. The Kernel density estimation reveals a clear difference between spatial distribution of the single-family house and second home construction in the study region. The single-family house construction is mainly concentrated in Joensuu region, while the second home construction is more dispersed around the shores of the biggest lakes in North Karelia.

Most of the single-family house construction has concentrated in Joensuu region. A total of 1,892 new single-family houses, which accounts for 87.8% of all new single-family houses in the study region, were constructed in Joensuu region in 2011-2019 (Figures 10 and 11). In other sub-regions in the region, Central Karelia and Pielinen Karelia, the construction of the new single-family houses has been minor. In total 163 and 100 new single-family houses were constructed in Central Karelia and Pielinen Karelia, respectively. These numbers account for 8.8 and 4.6 per cent of the regional total. These proportions are much smaller than the proportions of these regions from the population of the whole North Karelia. In 2019, the population proportions were 10.3% and 12.7% for Central Karelia and Pielinen Karelia, respectively.

The construction activity of second homes is higher than the construction activity of single-family houses in rural areas of North Karelia (Figure 11). The proportions of Central Karelia and Pielinen Karelia from the total construction of second homes in North Karelia were 25.2% (N=217 second homes) and 22.9% (N=185 second homes), respectively. The numbers of second homes built in these sub-regions exceed the numbers of single-family houses built. However, it should be noted that the total number of the second homes built in North Karelia was 948, which is 46% of the number of single-family houses. In Joensuu region, the construction of the second homes concentrates on rural areas, accounting for 95.1% of the second homes built in Joensuu region (Figure 11).

Figure 10 Location of the wood construction projects in North Karelia analysed with GIS.

Figure 11 Volume of wood construction in North Karelia.

4.2.4 Investment data for construction of single-family houses and second homes

The investment (budget) data for the wood construction were gathered from different stakeholders, including construction companies and local planning organizations. In example calculation, we used the price of 157,564€ for a single-family house and 139,620€ for a second home, based on **scenario A (wooden components are produced in the region)** (Table 12). The results are also calculated in **scenario B (wooden components are produced outside of the region)** to evaluate the employment impacts of the local wood processing and house manufacturing industries. In scenario B, the cost of the house package is reduced from the total cost of second home and single-family house.

Table 12 Estimated average cost of second home and single-family house construction in North Karelia. Source: Lehtonen & Okkonen (2013).

<i>Component</i>	<i>Single-family house</i>	<i>Second home</i>	<i>Industry in regional input-output table</i>
Cost [€]			
House package	84,734	67,800	Manufacture of wood and of products of wood and cork, except furniture; manufacture of articles of straw and plaiting materials
Working hours	14,030	13,020	Construction
Concrete	3,000	3,000	Manufacture of non-metal mineral products
Kitchen	6,000	6,000	Wholesale and retail trade
Building service technology	13,800	13,800	Construction
Other accessory and timber	18,000	18,000	Wholesale and retail trade
Decoration	9,000	9,000	Wholesale and retail trade
Assorted cost	9,000	9,000	Construction
Sum	157,564	139,620	

The total investment in construction of wooden single-family houses and second homes was 456.9 million € in North Karelia in the period 2011-2019. This means an average investment of approximately 320 €/person/year, which is approximately double the sum invested in buying milk. The within-region geographical variation is high, since as much as 361.0 million € (79%) of the total investments was concentrated in Joensuu region. The investment values for Pielinen Karelia and Central Karelia were 45.3 and 50.2 million €, respectively. In total 42% of the investments took place in urban and 58% in rural areas. Of the total rural area investments, 64% were directed to Joensuu region, 19% to Central Karelia, and 17% to Pielinen Karelia. Being the only urban region in North Karelia, Joensuu region accounted for 100% of the urban region building value. Figure 12 visualizes the distribution of wood construction investments in North Karelia. Most of the investments, as well as socio-economic impacts, take place in construction sector. According to a previous study (Lehtonen & Okkonen 2013), companies operating are mostly located within a 30-km radius, thus increasing the regional socio-economic impacts of the construction project.

Figure 12 The regional investments of the wood construction in North Karelia in 2011-2019 in scenario A (building components are produced in the region).

4.2.5 Regional input-output model estimating socio-economic impacts

A regional input-output model is an application of the neo-classical theory of general equilibrium to the empirical analysis of the interdependence between economic sectors, such as industries, consumption and exports, and compensations for households and imports. It was originally developed to analyze the connections between different industries within a national economy (Leontief 1966, 134), and is a useful tool for showing the structure of the economy in terms of the flows of goods and services, and for analyzing the impacts of changes in their demand.

The input-output model is applied to assess the employment impacts the wood construction. The model takes as initial assumptions that industrial outputs are determined by the final demand as linear functions of inputs from other industries, labor, capital, and imports. The model is written as

$$x = (I - A)^{-1} y \tag{1}$$

in which term A is an $n \cdot n$ matrix of input coefficients for n industries, $(I - A)^{-1}$ is known as the Leontief inverse. The vector y is the final demand for the output of each industry, and x is the column vector of gross outputs for each industry.

The regional input-output model for North Karelia is constructed from the relevant input-output statistics (Statistics Finland 2006). The base year of the regional input-output tables in Finland is 2002 but the vectors for gross outputs, final demand, employment, and employee compensation in the region were updated annually from the Regional Accounting (Statistics Finland 2021). The economic impact calculation uses regional data from 2011 until 2019, and all the vector data described earlier was updated for those years. Therefore, the employment and income multipliers change annually, which should improve the quality of the results and decline the overestimation of employment and income impacts. In this respect, the regional model applied considers productivity gains but still it is necessary to point out that the input-output modelling is not best suited for time series analysis of the socio-economic impacts. However, it is widely used in regional analyses because it can be used easily and quickly and can also be combined with other statistical analyses such as time series analysis and Difference in differences (DiD) impact analysis.

4.2.6 Employment impacts of wood construction in North Karelia

Wood construction may have positive effects on the regional labour market by, firstly, introducing investments on the wooden component production and construction of second homes, and, secondly, by supporting related industries and the employment therein (e.g., the retail trade, contractors, installers, and service providers). To estimate the employment impacts of the wood construction in North Karelia, we used type I input-output coefficients. The total employment impacts of construction of single-family houses and second homes were 3,676 and 1,500 person years, respectively.

The results show that most of the employment impacts are allocated in the urban areas of Joensuu region (Figure 13). The employment impacts in Joensuu region correspond to 81.7% of the total employment impact of wood construction. However, there is distinct variation between single-family house and second home constructions, since the proportion of Joensuu region is 89.5% of the total single-family house impacts and only 62.6% of the total second home impacts. The annual impacts of the wood construction are 470, 47, and 57 jobs in Joensuu region, Central Karelia, and Pielinen Karelia, respectively.

In Central Karelia and Pielinen Karelia, the employment impacts of second home construction are higher than the employment impacts of single-family house construction. This highlights the importance of the seasonal population for the local economies of Central Karelia and Pielinen Karelia.

Figure 13 Estimated employment impacts of the wood construction in North Karelia in scenario A (building components are produced in the region).

Figure 14 visualizes the differences between scenarios A and B in employment impacts, *i.e.*, how many regional jobs are created while producing the building components in the region instead of importing them from outside the region. Urban areas would benefit most from the use of local wooden components. In total, the use of local wooden components would have generated 1,616 jobs in urban areas in Joensuu region during the study period of 2011-2019. In Central Karelia and Pielinen Karelia the respective numbers would be 216 and 254, including only the construction activities of single-family houses and second homes. If the local wooden components are not used in the construction, the employment impacts would be halved.

Figure 14 Effect of regional production of building components on employment in sub-regions of North Karelia, Finland between 2011 and 2019. Differences in employment impacts between scenarios A (building components are produced in the region) and B (building components are procured outside of the region).

4.3 Lessons learned and future analyses in WP7

In terms of the pilot regions, this report is of descriptive character, framing the background and methodologies to assess the socio-economic impacts of wood construction in the regions. Region of North Karelia, Finland, is used as a case to illustrate the analysis of socio-economic impacts. Furthermore, this report is limited to single-family house and second home construction, whereas linked apartment houses, multi-storey apartment houses, schools, offices, agricultural buildings, etc. are not included. Forthcoming work in BASAJAUN WP7 *Open innovation platform and rural-urban pilot demonstrators* will widen the scope of modelling into the other regions and building types.

The analysis presented in chapter 4.2 is a case study on the regional input-output modelling of the socio-economic impacts of single-family house and second home construction in the case region. The results indicate that wood construction possesses a high potential for local economic development in North Karelia, particularly in Joensuu region, where most construction took place in the study period of 2011-2019. Based on the results, most of the employment impacts were allocated on urban areas because of the centralized development processes, while the impacts on rural areas were marginal.

Locality of wood construction means local employment impacts. Use of locally produced construction materials and construction-related services maximizes the regional employment impacts (see: Lanvin *et al.* 2020, BASAJAUN D1.1). Because the construction activity is minor in rural areas, the socio-

economic impacts could be increased by developing local sawn timber and construction element production. Development of wood-based component production should have high priority in regional development strategies. The potential socio-economic impacts in rural areas are further enhanced by the construction of second homes, which are an important part of the rural economy particularly in Finland and in the other Nordic countries.

The case of North Karelia demonstrates that GIS analysis and regional input-output modelling can be combined to assess the employment impacts of wood construction. However, the modelling approach must be further developed by adding what-if scenarios for wood construction and location of the wooden component industries and their production within the region. The potential socio-economic impacts of different scenarios for rural areas can then be analysed with Differences-in-differences (DiD) modelling to holistically see the impacts of wood construction and component production on the employment in rural areas, as well as impacts on future development. Such combination of the modelling approaches will be tested in WP7, which broadens the socio-economic impact analysis from Finland to France and Poland and expands the scope from single-family houses and second homes to other building types. Regions typically have different economic and demographic profiles, as well as different strategic interest toward wood construction. Thus, it is of high regional interest to evaluate the “wood construction footprint” on regional economies not only in the international context but also between different regions in on country. In case of Finland, WP7 will result in a comparison between the regions of North Karelia and Northern Ostrobothnia.

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Basajaun is a European innovation action about sustainable building with wood. The main objective is to demonstrate how wood construction chains can be optimized to foster both rural development and urban transformation whilst being connected with sustainable forest management in Europe. The consortium comprises 29 partners from 12 countries including 8 leading research and technology organizations, 3 universities, 15 companies and 4 other public and sectoral organizations. The project is coordinated by the Tecnalia Research and Innovation Foundation in Spain

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